

**Reference List for: Röhner, J., & Schütz, A. (2021). Psychologie der
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Abstract

This document contains the full reference list from the audio book: “Röhner, J., & Schütz, A. (2021). Psychologie der Kommunikation (J. Bönsch, Sprecherin) [Hörbuch]. Springer.” The reference list is provided here separately to help researchers find the cited works more easily.

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